

LOVE, HATE, CONSPIRACY, AND RACISM IN SHAKESPEARE'S OTHELLO

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ABSTRACT

William Shakespeare is regarded as the greatest writer and a playwright of English language. Though he belongs to England but there could be hardly any region which fails to recognize him. Even in Indian literature and creative world he is the most respected writer. He explored the human nature and their behavior through his imaginary characters. Even after 400 years, the creative writers, directors, filmmakers and art world take inspiration from his writings and recreate their characters. He started writing plays in light and comical ways but after a few years he created tragic plays and stories which are regarded as the finest works of English literature. His all-time famous plays are Hamlet, Macbeth, and Othello. These plays and its characters are full of love, hatred, and conspiracy. They have the power of unfading impression which leave a non-erasable and indelible marks in the minds of the readers. It's normally said that a writer expresses his views and create a world of imagination of his time but Shakespeare works and characters were always ahead of its time. His plays are timeless masterpieces which can never fade away.

KEYWORDS: Timeless Masterpiece, Greatest Playwright, Indelible Marks.

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